

A review of the synanthropic spiders from South Africa (Arachnida: Araneae)

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ABSTRACT: Spiders are frequently encountered in houses and outbuildings in South Africa. With the warm subtropical climate, houses, windows, and security doors are frequently left open, allowing spiders to enter freely. Data for this review were obtained from museum databases and primary specimen data were collected with specimens and extracted from published revisions. A total of 86 synanthropic species from 22 spider families have so far been recorded from buildings in South Africa, of which 17 species are hemisynanthropic and 56 are asynanthropic species that are accidentally recorded from buildings but only 13 species are eusynanthropic species living exclusively in buildings. Many of the species regularly found associated with buildings are introduced species.

Key notes: alien species, asynanthropic, eusynanthropic, hemisynanthropic, South African National Survey of Arachnida.

INTRODUCTION

Information on spiders in urban areas has increased in the last 20 years, especially in Europe and North America. A number of publications deal with synanthropic spiders (Cutler, 1973; Kaston, 1983; Taucare-Ríos *et al.*, 2013) but many focused on species that live in man-made habitats like gardens and crops, and not especially in houses. Only a few studies restricted the observations to spiders found in houses. Smithers (1990) recorded house spiders in the Plymouth area (UK), Guarisco (1999) studied these animals in Kansas (USA), Armas (2003) provided an account of spiders in a house in Cuba, and Jocqué *et al.* (2016) in Belgium. From Africa the first information on synanthropic species was provided by Dippenaar-Schoeman & Jocqué (1997).

As part of the South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSA) (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2015), data have been collected on species distribution in urban areas. With the introduction of the SANSA Virtual Museum (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2012) and the Spider Identification Service at the Agricultural Research Council, National Collection of Arachnida (NCA), we obtained information on synanthropic species in South Africa.

More than 10 000 records of spiders recorded from buildings were extracted from databases based on primary data collected with specimens housed in natural history collections of the NCA and the National Museum in Bloemfontein. The checklist (Table 1) includes references to taxonomic papers of species confirming their presence in houses and on the outside of houses.

Spiders associated with houses and outbuildings can be conveniently divided into three categories, according to Rozwałka (2006):

Eusynanthropic species (ES) – species living exclusively in man-made areas. They are true synanthropes associated with houses, where they live and breed. Many of the species have very wide global distributions because they are often accidentally transported to new areas. They seldom occur locally in the natural environment.

Hemisynanthropic species (HS) – species commonly found in synanthropic environments, although they often occur in natural environments as well. It includes species that are seasonally abundant in natural habitats and in houses. Although some may hibernate indoors, and the emergence of large numbers of spiderlings from an occasional egg sac may give the impression of an infestation, these species do not establish populations inside houses.

Asynanthropic species (AS) – spiders occurring in natural conditions, and they are only occasionally found in buildings.

In this paper we present a checklist of spider families and species associated with buildings in South Africa.

Figure 1. *Selenops radiatus* Latreille, 1819, a eusynanthropic species commonly found in houses in some provinces of South Africa. Photo: Peter Webb.

Figure 2. *Oecobius navus* Blackwall, 1859, a eusynanthropic species found throughout South Africa in houses. Photo: Peter Webb.

RESULTS

A total of 22 spider families and 82 species have been recorded from buildings in South Africa. Most of the species (54) are asynanthropic species and are only accidentally found in synanthropic environments. Several species (15) are hemisynanthropic species that spend some time in a synanthropic environment, but they are found in natural conditions as well. Only a few species (13) are eusynanthropic and in South Africa they are exclusively associated with buildings.

Of the 2 253 species of spiders presently recorded from South Africa (Foord *et al.*, 2020), 74 species are cosmopolitan or introduced. Introductions of species beyond their natural range are rising because of the increasing trade, transport, travel, and tourism connected to globalisation.

Species from the following families have been recorded:

1. AGELENIDAE

Three introduced species of the genus *Tegenaria* are synanthropic and found in buildings in South Africa (Dippenaar-Schoeman & Jocqué, 1997). Lawrence (1964) was the first to report that *Tegenaria* spp. are occasionally found in houses in Cape Town. The three introduced species (Table 1) were recorded in and around outbuildings in the Gauteng, Mpumalanga, Eastern Cape, and Western Cape provinces of South Africa (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2021a).

2. ARANEIDAE

A large number of araneid species are commonly found in gardens but only single species are sometimes accidentally carried into houses but that is very rare. It is mainly the cosmopolitan hermit spider *Nephilingis cruentata* (Fabricius, 1775) that make their large orb-web spider with a funnel retreat under the overhang of roofs in Limpopo, Mpumalanga, and KwaZulu-Natal (Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2014, 2023; Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2022b).

3. CHEIRACANTHIDAE

The genus *Cheiracanthium* was revised by Lotz (1995, 2007) and it is mainly the African endemic species *C. furculatum* Karsch, 1879 that are commonly found in house throughout South Africa (Dippenaar-Schoeman & Lotz, 2017; Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2021b; 2021f). During the day they are found in a soft silk retreats usually made in folds of fabric or in the corners of walls and ceilings, but at night they wander around in search of food and then land in beds and, when threatened, they may administer bites (Newlands, 1975, 1976, 1977, 1978).

4. CLUBIONIDAE

Clubionids are free-living, nocturnal hunters commonly found on vegetation. They make sac-like retreats in rolled-up vegetation and grasses. The genus was revised by Mbo (2022) and he reports two species that have been sampled from houses in Bloemfontein and Pretoria.

5. DEINOPIDAE

Menneus camelus Pocock, 1902, a South African endemic species, catch moths with expandable webs and were frequently encountered in houses, usually in bathrooms in South Africa, as reported by Coddington *et al.* (2012); Dippenaar-Schoeman (2014); Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.* (2020a).

6. DESIDAE

Badumna longinqua L. Koch, 1867, a species native to Australia, make cribellate webs between leaves and hollow areas, and are commonly found around houses (Fig. 3). Only one species has recently been introduced into South Africa, where it constructs webs on walls and roofs (Haddad, 2011, 2012; Haddad & Foord, 2021).

Badumna longinqua has been sampled from the southern coastal areas (Eastern and Western Cape provinces) and central Free State province, with almost all of the records associated with synanthropic urban habitats (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2021c).

Figure 3. *Badumna longinqua*. a. Female b. Retreats on roof. Photos: C. Haddad.

7. DICTYNIDAE

Brigittea civica (Lucas, 1850), an introduced species (Fig. 4c), was discovered for the first time in Pretoria in 2011 (Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2012a; Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2020c). It is a web dweller that makes retreat-webs on walls (Fig. 4b). The spider takes up position in the middle of the web and the web consists of sticky threads radiating outwards (Fig. 4a). They made quite a mess on a building at Roodeplaat (Fig. 4b).

Figures 4 a-c. *Brigittea civica* with webs. Photos: P. Webb.

8. DRYMUSIDAE

Izithunzi capense (Simon, 1893) is a Western Cape endemic species that usually hangs beneath loose space webs and are found hidden in wall crevices or below leaf litter and has been reported to wander inside houses in Cape Town (iNaturalist).

9. DYSDERIDAE

Dysdera crocata C.L. Koch, 1838 is a cosmopolitan species that is often associated with human habitations (Cooke, 1965). Although *D. crocata* has been introduced into most countries worldwide and often encountered in and around houses, it is not widespread in the Afrotropical Region. In South Africa it has been found in houses in the Western Cape and Gauteng (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2020b).

10. FILISTATIDAE

Filistatids are nocturnal spiders, living in tubular silk-lined retreats in crevices in rocks or walls. The species *Andoharano ansieae* Zonstein & Marusik, 2015 was for the first time recorded from houses in Gravelotte and Hoedspruit in the eastern part of Limpopo

(Eichhoff *et al.*, 2021; Figure 5. *Andoharano ansieae*. Photo: A. Eichhoff.

11. GNAPHOSIDAE

The Gnaphosidae is a large family of ground dwellers and only a few gnaphosid species are known to share human habitations. Two synanthropic species, *Marinarozelotes jaxartensis* (Kroneberg, 1875) and *Urozelotes rusticus* (L. Koch, 1872), have been transported by humans to many parts of the world, occurring in houses and disturbed habitats in regions with warm climates (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2021d). In a recent revision of *Afrodrassex* (Haddad & Booysen, 2022), the majority of the specimens of the species *A. balrog* Haddad & Booysen, 2022 were collected inside houses and gardens in central South Africa at night.

12. MITURGIDAE

Specimens of *Parapostenus* have been sampled from Hogsback but the taxonomy of the genus is still unresolved (Haddad *et al.*, in press).

13. OECOBIIDAE

Several species of *Oecobius* are synanthropic and two cosmopolitan species, *O. navus* Blackwall, 1859 (Fig. 2) and *O. putus* O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1876 (Fig. 6), are known from the Afrotropical Region and South Africa. *Oecobius navus* has the widest distribution and is found throughout South Africa, associated with buildings (Dippenaar-Schoeman & Jocqué, 1997; Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2021e, 2022b).

Figure 6. *Oecobius putus*. Photo: R. Steenkamp

14. OONOPIDAE

Some oonopids are found in association with dry material, for example in hay-sheds and bird nests. They even occur in dry insect collections where they probably prey on *Acarus* mites. In South Africa, the African endemic species *Opopaea speciosa* (Lawrence, 1952) has been sampled from thatched roofs in Mpumalanga, where they were present in large numbers dropping down on the furniture (Dippenaar-Schoeman & Jocqué, 1997).

15. PHOLCIDAE

Pholcids are commonly found in human habitations and several species have been recorded from South Africa. *Artema atlanta* Walckenaer, 1837 occurs throughout Africa (Huber, 2003) and the species has been reported from localities in the Northern Cape and Mpumalanga (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2010). *Crossopriza lyoni* (Blackwall, 1867), a cosmopolitan species, was the first time reported from South Africa by Huber (2003) (Fig. 7a). It has since been recorded from Pretoria (Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2009), where they were present in high numbers covering the walls and ceiling with their webbing (Fig. 7b). *Smeringopus natalensis* Lawrence, 1947 and *S. lotzi* Huber, 2012 are common species sampled from houses in South Africa (Huber, 2012; Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2014, 2023).

Figures 7. *Crossopriza lyoni*. a. Female. b. Webbing Photos: P. Marais.

16. PISAURIDAE

Pisaurid species are commonly found in gardens and some of the species sometimes wander into residences, e.g. *Rothus aethiopicus* (Pavesi, 1883). Jones (2016) reported on a female *Euprosphenops australis* Simon, 1898 breeding in a house in the Free State. A species regularly recorded from houses in that province.

17. SALTICIDAE

Salticids are commonly found in gardens and possibly most of the 23 species reported from buildings are accidental visitors. Only the cosmopolitan species such as *Hasarius adansoni* (Audouin, 1826) and *Menemerus bivittatus* Dufour, 1831 are frequently encountered in houses and other buildings (Dippenaar-Schoeman & Jocqué, 1997; Dippenaar-Schoeman 2014, 2023).

18. SCYTODIDAE

Two cosmopolitan species, *Scytodes fusca* Walckenaer 1837 and *S. thoracica* Latreille 1802, are mentioned in the literature to occur in houses (Lawrence, 1964; Dippenaar-Schoeman & Jocqué, 1997; Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2021g). However, in a revision of *Scytodes* presently under way (Booyesen [pers.com]), only *S. elizabethae* Purcell, 1904 and *S. univittata* Simon, 1882 are frequently associated with buildings in South Africa.

19. SELENOPIIDAE

Nine selenopid species have been identified as synanthropic and are among the most common spiders encountered on walls in South Africa. When disturbed they disappear under wall hangings or into crevices. Their round, flat, papery egg-sacs are frequently seen on wooden beams (Croeser, 1979). Visser (1993a,b) reported on the occurrence of *Selenops radiatus* Latreille, 1819 in potato sheds in South Africa where it preys on the potato tuber moth, cockroaches, and silverfish (Corronco, 2002; Dippenaar-Schoeman & Jocqué, 1997, Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2020e).

20. SICARIIDAE

Loxosceles spp. are not web-bound spiders and spin only a few irregular strands of silk that serve as retreats made under objects on the ground or in dark corners in buildings, outbuildings, and caves (Newlands, 1975). Four *Loxosceles* species have been recorded from buildings: *L. dejagerae* Lotz, 2017, *L. simillima* Lawrence, 1927, *L. spinulosa* Purcell, 1904, and *L. parramae* Newlands, 1981 (Fig. 8.). In some houses in Bloemfontein *L. simillima* is frequently found in houses. (Newlands, 1980; Lotz, 2012 & 2017; Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2021h).

Figure 8. *Loxosceles parramae* from Kempton Park. Photo: W. Schmidt.

21. SPARASSIDAE

In the Sparassidae it is mainly *Palystes* spp. that are usually associated with buildings. From the revision of *Palystes* by Croeser (1996), seven species have been sampled from suburban gardens and buildings in Southern Africa. They are commonly known as rain spiders as they wander into houses during the rainy season. Two of the species are very commonly encountered in houses, namely *P. castaneus* (Latreille, 1819) in the southwestern Cape, particularly the Cape Peninsula, and *P. superciliosus* L. Koch, 1875 that occurs throughout South Africa (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2022a).

22. THERIDIIDAE

Many theridiids are associated with buildings. The preferred web sites are usually on stone walls and crevices in house walls and window frames and seven species are listed in Table 1. The larger *Latrodectus* species are frequently encountered and the introduced *Latrodectus geometricus* C.L. Koch, 1841 is very commonly found in built-up areas, usually outside houses where they make their webs in dark areas such as under window sills and verandas. *Latrodectus renivulvatus* Dahl, 1902 is less common in built-up areas but specimens have been collected from inside houses in Gauteng (Lotz, 1994; Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2021d, e).

23. TRACHELIDAE

In the Trachelidae, three *Afrocto* species and two *Orthobula* species have been sampled from buildings. They are, however, synanthropic species that are only accidentally found in buildings (Lyle & Haddad, 2010; Haddad *et al.*, 2022).

24. TROCHANTERIIDAE

The Trochanteriidae species are free-living wanderers with flattened bodies, adapted to life in narrow crevices. *Platyoides walteri* Karsch, 1886, the most common species in Southern Africa, is synanthropic and frequently encountered in buildings, often found underneath plant containers on verandahs (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2022c).

25. ULOBORIDAE

Several uloborid species have a cosmopolitan distribution and are frequently found in and around houses. The following species are recorded from the Afrotropical Region: *Uloborus plumipes* Lucas, 1846; *U. walckenaerius* Latreille, 1806, and *Zosis geniculata* Olivier (Dippenaar-Schoeman & Jocqué, 1997). In South Africa especially *Uloborus plumipes* is commonly found in buildings (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2020f).

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TABLE 1. Spider species found in buildings in South Africa. ST status: ES eusynanthropic species; HS hemisynanthropic species; AS asynanthropic species. AD abundance R rare; c common; VC very common.

SPECIES	ST	AB	REFERENCES
1. AGELENIDAE			
<i>Tegenaria domestica</i> (Clerck, 1757)	ES	R	Lawrence (1964); Dippenaar-Schoeman & Jocqué (1997); Dippenaar-Schoeman (2014); Dippenaar-Schoeman <i>et al.</i> (2021a)
<i>Tegenaria pagana</i> C.L. Koch, 1840	ES	R	Le Roux & Dippenaar-Schoeman (2016)
<i>Tegenaria parietina</i> (Fourcroy, 1785)	ES	R	Dippenaar-Schoeman <i>et al.</i> (2021a)
2. ARANEIDAE			
<i>Nephilingis cruentata</i> (Fabricius, 1775)	HS	C	Dippenaar-Schoeman & Jocqué (1997); Dippenaar-Schoeman (2014); Dippenaar-Schoeman <i>et al.</i> (2022b); Holm & Dippenaar-Schoeman (2010)
3. CHEIRACANTHIIDAE			
<i>Cheiracanthium furculatum</i> Karsch, 1879	HS	VC	Dippenaar-Schoeman & Jocqué (1997); Lotz (1995, 2007); Dippenaar-Schoeman (2014; 2023); Dippenaar-Schoeman & Lotz (2017); Dippenaar-Schoeman <i>et al.</i> (2021b, 2021f); Newlands (1975)
4. CLUBIONIDAE			
<i>Clubiona</i> (undescribed new sp.)	AS	R	Mbo (2022)
<i>Clubiona revillioidi</i> Lessert, 1936	AS	R	Mbo (2022)
5. DEINOPIIDAE			
<i>Menneus camelus</i> Pocock, 1902	AS	R	Coddington <i>et al.</i> (2012); Dippenaar-Schoeman & Jocqué (1997); Dippenaar-Schoeman (2014); Dippenaar-Schoeman <i>et al.</i> (2020a)
6. DESIDAE			
<i>Badumna longinqua</i> L. Koch, 1867	ES	C	Haddad (2011, 2012); Haddad & Foord (2021); Dippenaar-Schoeman <i>et al.</i> (2021c)
7. DICTYNIDAE			
<i>Brigittea civica</i> (Lucas, 1850)	ES	R	Dippenaar-Schoeman (2012a); Dippenaar-Schoeman <i>et al.</i> (2020c)
8. DRYMUSIDAE			
<i>Izithunzi capense</i> (Simon, 1893)	HS	R	Anecdotal, Spider Club face book
9. DYSDERIDAE			
<i>Dysdera crocata</i> C.L. Koch, 1838	AS	R	Dippenaar-Schoeman & Jocqué (1997); Dippenaar-Schoeman <i>et al.</i> (2020b)
10. FILISTATIDAE			
<i>Andoharano ansieae</i> Zonstein & Marusik, 2015	HS	R	Eichhoff <i>et al.</i> (2021); Dippenaar-Schoeman <i>et al.</i> (2023a)
11. GNAPHOSIDAE			
<i>Afrodrassex balrog</i> Haddad & Booysen, 2022	AS	C	Haddad & Booysen, 2022
<i>Marinarozelotes jaxartensis</i> (Kroneberg, 1875)	AS	C	Dippenaar-Schoeman & Jocqué (1997); Dippenaar-Schoeman <i>et al.</i> (2021d)
<i>Urozelotes rusticus</i> (L. Koch, 1872)	AS	C	Dippenaar-Schoeman & Jocqué (1997); Dippenaar-Schoeman <i>et al.</i> (2021d)
12. MITURGIDAE			
<i>Parapostenus</i> sp. (undetermined)	AS	R	Haddad <i>et al.</i> (2023) (Hogsback)
13. OECOBIIDAE			
<i>Oecobius navus</i> Blackwall, 1859	ES	VC	Lawrence (1964); Dippenaar-Schoeman & Jocqué (1997); Dippenaar-Schoeman <i>et al.</i> (2021e, 2022b)
<i>Oecobius putus</i> O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1876	AS	R	Dippenaar-Schoeman <i>et al.</i> (2021e, 2022b)
14. OONOPIIDAE			
<i>Opopaea speciosa</i> (Lawrence, 1952)	AS	R	Dippenaar-Schoeman & Jocqué (1997)
15. PHOLCIDAE			
<i>Artema atlanta</i> Walckenaer, 1837	HS	R	Dippenaar-Schoeman & Jocqué (1997); Huber (2003)
<i>Crossopriza lyoni</i> (Blackwall, 1867)	ES	R	Huber (2003; 2009); Dippenaar-Schoeman (2012)
<i>Smeringopus lotzi</i> Huber, 2012	HS	VC	Huber (2012); Dippenaar-Schoeman (2014)
<i>Smeringopus natalensis</i> Lawrence, 1947	HS	VC	Holm & Dippenaar-Schoeman (2010); Dippenaar-Schoeman (2014)
16. PISAURIDAE			
<i>Euprosthonops australis</i> Simon, 1898	AS	R	Jones (2016); Dippenaar-Schoeman <i>et al.</i> (2020d)
<i>Rothus aethiopicus</i> (Pavesi, 1883)	AS	R	Dippenaar-Schoeman <i>et al.</i> (2020d)
17. SALTICIDAE			
<i>Baryphas ahenus</i> Simon, 1902	AS	C	Haddad & Wesotowska (2011)
<i>Evarcha ignea</i> Wesotowska & Cumming, 2008	AS	C	Wesotowska & Cumming (2008); Dippenaar-Schoeman (2023)
<i>Evarcha zimbabwensis</i> Wesotowska & Cumming, 2008	AS	C	Wesotowska & Cumming (2008)

SPECIES	ST	AB	REFERENCES
<i>Hasarius adansoni</i> (Audouin, 1826)	HS	VC	Dippenaar-Schoeman & Jocqué (1997); Dippenaar-Schoeman (2014; 2023); Wesolowska & Cumming (2008)
<i>Heliophanus debilis</i> Simon, 1901	AS	R	Wesolowska & Cumming (2008)
<i>Heliophanus demonstrativus</i> Wesolowska, 1986	AS	R	Wesolowska (1986)
<i>Holcolaetis vellerea</i> Simon, 1909	AS	R	Wesolowska & Cumming (2008)
<i>Heliophanus transvaalicus</i> Simon, 1901	AS	R	Haddad & Wesolowska (2011)
<i>Hyllus argyrotoxicus</i> Simon, 1902	AS	R	Wesolowska & Cumming (2008); Wesolowska & Haddad (2009)
<i>Hyllus dotata</i> (Peckham & Peckham, 1903)	AS	R	Wesolowska & Cumming (2008)
<i>Hyllus treleaveni</i> Peckham & Peckham, 1902	AS	R	Wesolowska & Haddad (2009)
<i>Icius insolitus</i> (Wesolowska, 1999)	AS	R	Wesolowska & Cumming (2008)
<i>Menemerus carlini</i> Peckham & Peckham, 1903	AS	R	Wesolowska & Cumming (2008)
<i>Menemerus bifurcus</i> Wesolowska, 1999	AS	R	Wesolowska (1999)
<i>Menemerus bivittatus</i> Dufour, 1831	HS	VC	Lawrence (1942); Wesolowska (1999); Dippenaar-Schoeman & Jocqué (1997); Dippenaar-Schoeman (2014)
<i>Menemerus transvaalicus</i> Wesolowska, 1999	AS	R	Haddad & Wesolowska (2011; Dippenaar-Schoeman (2014)
<i>Mexcala elegans</i> Peckham & Peckham, 1903	AS	R	Dippenaar-Schoeman (2014; 2023); Wesolowska & Haddad (2009)
<i>Myrmarachne laurentina</i> Bacelar, 1953	AS	R	Wesolowska & Haddad (2009)
<i>Natta horizontalis</i> Karsch, 1879	AS	R	Lawrence (1942); Wesolowska & Cumming (2008)
<i>Portia schultzi</i> Karsch, 1878	AS	R	Wesolowska & Cumming (2008)
<i>Rumburak laxus</i> (Zhang & Maddison, 2012)	AS	R	Dippenaar-Schoeman (2023)
<i>Rumburak mirabilis</i> Wesolowska, Azarkina & Russell-Smith, 2014	AS	R	Wesolowska, Azarkina & Russell-Smith (2014)
18. SCYTODIDAE			
<i>Scytodes fusca</i> Walckenaer 1837	ES	C	Dippenaar-Schoeman & Jocqué (1997); Dippenaar-Schoeman (2014); Dippenaar-Schoeman <i>et al.</i> (2021g)
<i>Scytodes elizabethae</i> Purcell, 1904	ES	C	Booyens (<i>Scytodes</i> revision in progress)
<i>Scytodes univittata</i> Simon, 1882	ES	C	Booyens (<i>Scytodes</i> revision in progress)
19. SELENOPIIDAE			
<i>Anyphops capensis</i> (Lawrence, 1940)	AS	R	Corronco (2002); Dippenaar-Schoeman <i>et al.</i> (2020e)
<i>Anyphops fitzsimonsi</i> (Lawrence, 1940)	AS	R	Lawrence (1940); Dippenaar-Schoeman <i>et al.</i> (2020e)
<i>Anyphops immaculatus</i> (Lawrence, 1940)	AS	R	Lawrence (1940); Dippenaar-Schoeman <i>et al.</i> (2020e)
<i>Anyphops marshalli</i> (Pocock, 1902)	AS	R	Dippenaar-Schoeman <i>et al.</i> (2020e)
<i>Anyphops stauntoni</i> Benoit, 1968	AS	R	Dippenaar-Schoeman <i>et al.</i> (2020e)
<i>Selenops alticolus</i> Lawrence, 1940	AS	R	Corronco (2002); Dippenaar-Schoeman <i>et al.</i> (2020e)
<i>Selenops krugeri</i> Lawrence, 1940	AS	R	Corronco (2002)
<i>Selenops tuckeri</i> Lawrence, 1940	AS	C	Lawrence (1940); Dippenaar-Schoeman <i>et al.</i> (2020e)
<i>Selenops radiatus</i> Latreille, 1819	ES	C	Visser (1993a,b); Dippenaar-Schoeman & Jocqué (1997); Dippenaar-Schoeman (2014; 2023); Corronco (2002)
20. SICARIIDAE			
<i>Loxosceles dejagerae</i> Lotz, 2017	AS	C	Lotz (2017)
<i>Loxosceles parramae</i> Newlands, 1981	ES	VC	Newlands (1975; 1980; 1981); Dippenaar-Schoeman & Jocqué (1997); Lotz (2012; 2017); Dippenaar-Schoeman <i>et al.</i> (2022a)
<i>Loxosceles simillima</i> Lawrence, 1927	AS	VC	Newlands (1975; 1986); Lotz (2017)
<i>Loxosceles spinulosa</i> Purcell, 1904	AS	VC	Newlands (1975); Lotz (2012; 2017)
21. SPARASSIDAE			
<i>Palystes castaneus</i> (Latreille, 1819)	AS	VC	Croeser (1996); Dippenaar-Schoeman <i>et al.</i> (2022a)
<i>Palystes karoensis</i> Croeser, 1996	AS	R	Croeser (1996)
<i>Palystes leppanae</i> Pocock, 1902	AS	C	Croeser (1996); Dippenaar-Schoeman <i>et al.</i> (2022a)
<i>Palystes leroyorum</i> Croeser, 1996	AS	R	Croeser (1996); Dippenaar-Schoeman <i>et al.</i> (2022a)
<i>Palystes perornatus</i> Pocock, 1900	AS	R	Croeser (1996); Dippenaar-Schoeman (2014); Dippenaar-Schoeman <i>et al.</i> (2022a)
<i>Palystes stuarti</i> Croeser, 1996	AS	R	Croeser (1996); Dippenaar-Schoeman <i>et al.</i> (2022a)
<i>Palystes superciliosus</i> L. Koch, 1875	HS	VC	Croeser (1996); Dippenaar-Schoeman (2014; 2023); Dippenaar-Schoeman <i>et al.</i> (2022a)

SPECIES	ST	AB	REFERENCES
22. THERIDIIDAE			
<i>Latrodectus geometricus</i> C.L. Koch, 1841	HS	VC	Lotz (1994); Dippenaar-Schoeman (2014; 2023); Dippenaar-Schoeman & Lotz (2017)
<i>Latrodectus renivulvatus</i> Dahl, 1902	HS	C	Lotz (1994); Dippenaar-Schoeman (2014); Dippenaar-Schoeman & Lotz (2017)
<i>Parasteatoda tepidariorum</i> (C. L. Koch, 1841)	ES	VC	Dippenaar-Schoeman <i>et al.</i> (2022d)
<i>Steatoda capensis</i> Hann, 1990	HS	C	Hann (1990); Dippenaar-Schoeman <i>et al.</i> (2022e)
<i>Theridion purcelli</i> O.P.-Cambridge, 1905	HS	VC	Lawrence (1964); Dippenaar-Schoeman (2014); Dippenaar-Schoeman <i>et al.</i> (2022e)
<i>Tidarren cuneolatum</i> (Tullgren, 1910)	HS	C	Knoflach & Harten van (2006); Dippenaar-Schoeman <i>et al.</i> (2022e)
<i>Enoplognatha molesta</i> O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1904	AS	C	Anecdotal, attch webs to building
23. TRACHELIDAE			
<i>Afrocto africana</i> (Simon, 1910)	AS	R	Lyle & Haddad (2010)
<i>Afrocto corcula</i> Lyle & Haddad, 2010	AS	R	Lyle & Haddad (2010)
<i>Afrocto martini</i> (Simon, 1897)	AS	R	Lyle & Haddad (2010)
<i>Orthobula arca</i> Haddad, Jin & Platnick, 2022	AS	R	Haddad, Jin & Platnick (2022)
<i>Orthobula radiata</i> Simon, 1897	AS	R	Haddad, Jin & Platnick (2022)
24. TROCHANTERIIDAE			
<i>Platyoides walteri</i> Karsch, 1886	HS	C	Dippenaar-Schoeman & Jocqué (1997); Dippenaar-Schoeman (2014; 2023)
25. ULOBORIDAE			
<i>Uloborus plumipes</i> Lucas, 1846	HS	VC	Dippenaar-Schoeman & Jocqué (1997); Dippenaar-Schoeman (2014); Dippenaar-Schoeman <i>et al.</i> (2020f)
<i>Uloborus walckenaerius</i> Latreille, 1806	AS	R	Dippenaar-Schoeman & Jocqué (1997); Dippenaar-Schoeman <i>et al.</i> (2020f)